

Surgical Innovation: A Cross-Sectional Study on the Attitudes of Medical Students Toward Robotic Surgery in Oman

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Introduction

Robotic surgery is among the most advanced forms of minimally invasive surgery and continues to expand globally. Despite increasing international adoption, perceptions among medical trainees in Oman remain unexplored. Understanding these perceptions is essential for guiding curriculum integration and national surgical innovation strategies. This study aimed to assess medical students' knowledge and the perspectives of a smaller subgroup of surgical clinicians regarding robotic surgery and its potential integration into medical education in Oman.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional observational study used a previously validated questionnaire adapted from an international study distributed electronically to Sultan Qaboos University (SQU) medical students and doctors working in surgical departments at Sultan Qaboos University Hospital (SQUH). A non-probability convenience sampling technique was used. Data were analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 27.0, with a significance level of $P < 0.05$.

Results

A total of 574 participants were included, the majority being medical students (90.4%). Practicing surgical clinicians represented a small proportion of respondents. Overall, 73.6% reported prior awareness of robotic surgery, yet 83.7% acknowledged insufficient knowledge. Most participants identified greater precision as the main advantage (68.2%) and higher cost as the primary disadvantage (83.4%). While hesitation toward undergoing robotic surgery was common, 81.1% supported its integration into the MD curriculum and 89% supported incorporation into residency programs. Most agreed that Oman should invest in and expand robotic surgery.

Conclusion

There is generally positive openness toward robotic surgery among predominantly medical student participants, accompanied by knowledge gaps and cost concerns. Structured educational planning is required to support informed and sustainable integration.

Keywords

Robotic surgery; Medical education; Surgical innovation; Attitudes; Oman; Minimally invasive surgery